

Assessing Social Capital in Academic Research Teams: a measurement instrument proposal

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Abstract

The increasing importance of multidisciplinary and scientific collaboration makes it necessary to explore the configuration and structure of relationships within researchers' teams. The academic social capital construct can be particularly useful to conceptualize these internal ties. Nevertheless, the majority of studies in the academic context have measured social capital through social network techniques, drawing on quantitative counts of encounters to measure relationships. This approach fails to measure more qualitative and behavioural dimensions of social capital, which also need to be accounted for to fully understand relational dynamics within research teams. Considering this, the paper aims to propose and validate an instrument to measure academic social capital that combines the two approaches. First, based on the consensus opinion of an expert panel (Delphi method), a questionnaire comprising 20 items was designed and implemented. The scale was complemented with sociometric questions for assessing position and interconnectivity within the network. Second, an exploratory factor analysis technique was applied. The designed instrument was specified as a second-order model with three first-order factors (relational dimension, cognitive dimension and structural dimension) and a second-order factor (social capital). The confirmatory factorial analysis verified that the proposed model fit the sample data, showing that it could be used to reliably measure academic social capital.

Keywords: social capital, academic research, factorial analysis, scale validation

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1. Introduction

The Triple Helix Model highlights the key role of the university research in creating and transferring knowledge to the society contributing to social development of territories (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff, 1999). Drawing on this idea, the European Union (EU) launched the Program Horizon 2020 (H2020), a continuation of previous FP7 program in an attempt to enhance both the dynamic character and the reactivity and also the excellence of EU research. Since its start-up in 2007, H2020 has funded more than 9,000 research projects out of more than 65,000 applicants, with an annual average budget around of €1.8 billion and a total program budget around of €13.1 billion. EU is aware that advanced research increasingly requires the presence of collaborative and multidisciplinary teams. Therefore, typically some conditions must be met by research teams from applicants such as be integrated by a multidisciplinary and different nationality member.

Literature on university research indicates that multidisciplinary positively affects the researchers' performance (Horwitz and Horwitz, 2007). However, the relationship between multidisciplinary and performance of researchers seems to be non-linear. On the one hand, multidisciplinary teams can benefit from a wide range of knowledge, skills, perspectives, information, ideas and opinions of the members (Horwitz and Horwitz, 2007). These teams, in general, have more creativity and more innovative solutions as a result of the integration of diverse information and different perspectives provided by team members (van Knippenberg et al., 2004). But diversity also entails coordination, cohesion and communication problems within the team (Cummings and Kiesler, 2005). In this context, a deeper knowledge of the internal dynamics of the teams could help reduce these negative effects of multidisciplinary and improve the positive aspects. The academic social capital construct can be particularly useful to conceptualize the configuration and structure of relationships within researchers' teams helping to solve coordination and communication problems among members (Lin, 2001; Clopton, 2011).

Research on the social capital embedded in social networks has received growing interest in the management and organizational literature. A large body of empirical studies has focused on the effects of social capital on diverse organizational performance measures at the organization (Yiu and Lau, 2008; Payne et al., 2011; Dahlander and McFarland, 2013; Casciaro and Lobo, 2015; Fonti and Maoret, 2016) and individual levels (Xiao and Tsui, 2007; Chen, Chang, and Hung 2008; Ben, 2016). Similarly, research has demonstrated that social capital affects the acquisition and exchange of information and knowledge (Reagans and McEvily, 2003; Anderson, 2008; Van den Hooff and Huysman, 2009; Hau et al., 2013; Yen et al., 2015). Nevertheless, in the academic context, empirical evidence on the effects of social capital on research results remains scarce (Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014).

In the literature, social capital is considered as multidimensional concept comprising the structural, relational and cognitive dimensions of social interactions (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). The majority of the studies exploring the social capital embedded in academic research teams have used social network techniques to analyse the configuration and structure of internal relationships within teams. As a consequence, few scales are available to research managers to assess academic social capital. In this paper, we propose a measurement instrument of social capital that combines both a scale and sociometric questions about the network. The application of network analysis techniques can offer us quantitative information about structural attributes of the network, while the use of scale to measure social capital provides a more qualitative and valuable vision of the construct. In effect, measure social capital through a scale allows us to assess the qualitative and behavioural dimensions of the construct, which must be considered in order to fully understand the relational dynamics within the research teams. We believe an instrument to measure social capital may be a useful tool to shed light on the underlying mechanisms that explain the building of the social capital of research teams. Social capital is a resource available to research team members that can be managed; greater knowledge of the role played by the different dimensions of social interactions in building social capital could help to improve a group's social capital.

The purpose of this paper is to propose and validate a measurement instrument that enables to assess social capital embedded in academic research teams. The information obtained through the instrument will allow obtaining a greater knowledge of how social capital affects internal processes and the performance of research teams. To achieve this goal, a research strategy with qualitative and quantitative phases was performed. First, qualitative research, including the design and content validity of a social capital questionnaire, was conducted. The questionnaire was designed using the consensus opinion of an expert panel about relevant issues for measuring social capital in the context of university research teams. The questionnaire was composed of 20 items related to a) the patterns of connections of group members with external research networks; b) the existence of trust, norms and sense of identity among group members; and c) the extent to which information and knowledge shared exist within the research group. The questionnaire was complemented with five sociometric questions for collecting quantitative data on internal ties and structural position of researchers in the network. Second, the quantitative phase of the empirical analysis was performed via factor analysis. First, an exploratory factorial analysis was performed to generate factors from the set of 20 items constituting the factor structure or model. Then, a confirmatory factorial analysis was performed to validate the psychometric properties of the scale.

This paper contributes to the extant literature by providing a valid and reliable measurement instrument of social capital dimensions in the context of academic research teams. In addition, the

proposed instrument may provide guidelines to enhance academic research teams' social capital and therefore, improve the internal mechanisms of coordination, reflecting on its research results. The rest of this paper is organized into four main sections. Section 2 concisely presents the theoretical background on academic social capital and research teams. Section 3 describes the empirical analysis conducted, including the design of the questionnaire to measure social capital in the academic context and the sample. Section 4 presents the results of the scale validity, and section 5 concludes with a discussion of the findings of the study.

2. Literature review

2.1. Social capital dimensions

Social capital is considered by researchers as one of the critical factors in the creation of knowledge (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Several papers point out that high level of social capital lead to high levels of creativity and innovative solutions at group level (Chen, Chang and Hung, 2008; Hu and Randel, 2014).

The academic research literature has focused mainly on measuring social capital embedded in collaborative research networks highlighting its effects on research results. Applying social network analysis, many of these papers have confirmed the strong relationship between social capital and research performance (Abbasi, Altmann, and Hossain, 2011; Li, Liao and Yen, 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt, 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014; Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila, 2016).

The concept of social capital was first discussed in the scientific literature in early works of Bourdieu (1985), Coleman (1988; 1990) and Burt (1992). Since then, the concept has rapidly evolved, and it has been widely applied in different fields of social sciences. As a consequence, different definitions of the concept from different approaches have been proposed (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Lin, 2001; Adler and Kwon, 2002). According to Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998:243), social capital is defined as "the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or social unit". These authors provide a useful framework for understanding social capital. The authors grouped social capital's resources into three highly interrelated dimensions—structural, relational and cognitive—that facilitate the creation and exchange of knowledge.

The structural dimension

The structural dimension refers to the patterns of connections between members of a research social network described in terms of network ties, network configuration and appropriable organization (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998).

Social network theory provides two different perspectives on social network structure: the structural holes and closure network approaches. The structural holes approach takes the view that holes in the social network structure allow flows of information from several previously unconnected sources to connect, creating networks that are efficient and rich in information benefits (Burt, 1992). The presence of structural holes represents an advantage for researchers who act as a bridge between contacts to which they are directly connected, while the others are connected only indirectly (Ahuja, 2000). This gives researchers access to a greater volume of information, making them attractive actors within their network of contacts.

The structural holes and the strength of weak ties (Granovetter, 1973) approaches are related (Burt, 1992). The strength of weak ties approach considers that weak ties provide information with superior benefits to strong ties because the former are usually related to larger networks. Larger size increases the number of structural holes and the efficiency of the network, while strong ties lead to more redundant information (Anderson, 2008).

Following Coleman (1988), closure networks promote the generation of a greater level of mutual trust and co-operation, thereby improving team performance (Reagans and Zuckerman, 2001). In dense networks, the actors have easier access to valuable information, and repeated and consistent information generates more trust. In this approach, strong ties provide greater incentive to co-operate, greater trust and easier transfer of information and knowledge between actors (Rowley, Behrens and Krackhardt, 2000; Uzzi, 1996).

As some papers show, the type of network structure influences the process of knowledge production by research teams, the optimal network structure being field-specific (Jansen, von Görtz and Heidler, 2010). For instance, Gonzalez-Brambila (2014) found that dense networks had a negative impact on the generation of new knowledge. Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt (2013) found a positive impact of structural holes in the number of citations of academic researchers but not in the number of publications. Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila (2016) pointed out that both structural holes and dense networks had a positive effect on publications and impact.

As Badar, Hite and Badir (2014) indicated, a network structure is necessary for creating bridges to facilitate communication and collaboration and to enable the flow of resources in members' networks. Structural social capital is highly interrelated with relational and cognitive social capital (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998), which reflects the capacity of actors within the network to exchange resources (Andrews, 2010).

The relational dimension

While structural social capital involves social relationships, relational social capital refers to the behavioural assets embedded in these relationships, although both social capital dimensions are linked (Tsai and Ghoshal, 1998). The relational dimension refers mainly to trust, norms, obligations and expectations, and identification created through the personal relationships between actors (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). These facets of social capital can form a solid foundation for the combination and exchange of knowledge, allowing people to access and exchange knowledge and motivating them to do so (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Trust and behavioural norms can prevent opportunistic behaviours that hinder the sharing of knowledge between actors, as argued by Coleman (1988).

The literature has paid special attention to trust, showing that high levels of trust facilitate social exchange, co-operation and knowledge sharing, increasing performance (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Renzl 2008). Trusting relationships develop from social relationships evolving and changing over time from calculus-based trust (based on behavioural consistency) to knowledge-based trust (based on behavioural predictability) and identification-based trust (based on complete empathy) (Lewicki and Bunker, 1996). Maintaining close and frequent social interaction allows actors to know each other better, sharing information and points of view and thus increasing their mutual trust (Tsai and Ghoshal, 1998). Direct ties between researchers stimulate the combination and exchange of knowledge, providing the strength of the relationships ‘the opportunity to develop jointly held resources’ (Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014:1612).

Cognitive dimension

The cognitive dimension includes resources that facilitate communication and understanding between parties (Chow and Chan, 2008; Zheng, 2010). According to Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998:244), the cognitive dimension ‘refers to those resources providing shared representations, interpretations, and systems of meaning among parties’.

Cognitive social capital can be analysed through the shared language and narratives that enable team members to understand each other. A shared language and codes facilitate mutual understanding (Choi, 2015), allow access to people and their information and improve the ability to combine information obtained through social exchange and knowledge sharing (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Huysman and Wulf, 2006). Similarly, shared narratives enable knowledge sharing and a team’s ability to combine knowledge (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Huysman and Wulf, 2006).

2.2 Academic research teams

Modern science is characterized by collaboration, teamwork and multidisciplinary (Rey-Rocha et al. 2006). A number of authors stress that scientific collaboration has grown considerably in recent decades, thereby increasing the number of co-authored papers and significantly reducing the number of single-authored papers (Abt, 2007). Scientific collaboration takes place both nationally and internationally, as well as with external partners such as professional network teams (Vabø et al. 2016). There are several motives for collaboration in research (Bozeman and Corley, 2004), one of which is the social capital of the partners (Lee and Bozeman, 2005). Social capital may facilitate collaboration, but collaboration in turn increases social capital, understood as trust, norms of reciprocity and networks (Wagner and Fernandez-Gimenez, 2009). Previous work has also shown that scientific collaboration has positive effects on productivity and the impact of research (Lee and Bozeman, 2005; Sooryamoorthy, 2009; Li, Liao and Yen, 2013).

In addition, research is increasingly carried out in large and multidisciplinary research teams in which researchers share workloads, expertise, skills, equipment and resources with other members (Falk-Krzesinski et al., 2011; Li, Liao and Yen, 2013). Indeed, research teams have gained relevance in research, as in many disciplines they are considered to be the basic research units (Perianes-Rodríguez et al., 2010). The creation and consolidation of research teams at the institutional level are relevant to the scientific systems of many countries (Rey-Rocha et al. 2006; Vabø et al., 2016).

However, the literature provides different conceptualizations of the term 'research team'. Vabø et al. (2016) argue that while the term traditionally described informal or formal collaboration, it currently also includes formal units at the organizational level. Cohen (1991) identifies two methodological patterns to delimit the concept of a research team: output-based and input-based methods. In output-based studies, teams 'are defined in terms of co-authorship or cross citation' (Cohen, 1991:413) and administrative or institutional affiliation is not necessary. In contrast, in input-based studies, teams 'are defined by existing administrative arrangements' (Cohen, 1991:413) and author affiliation is required to identify teams. A mix of both methods has been also used in the empirical literature to identify and classify research teams (Perianes-Rodríguez et al., 2010).

The research activity and performance of researchers are influenced not only by individual characteristics but also by contextual factors related to research team characteristics (Martin-Sempere, Garzón-García and Rey-Rocha, 2008). The latter include factors related to the size, composition or degree of consolidation of a research team, and such factors have been analysed as conditioning research performance (Rey-Rocha, Martin-Sempere and Garzón, 2002). Similarly, papers focusing on research teams have highlighted that social capital favours the creation of new knowledge, positively affecting research performance and impact (Li, Liao and

Yen, 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). Therefore, if universities are the largest producers of knowledge, and social capital embedded in collaborative research networks improves research outputs, more accurate measurement of the knowledge resources available to research teams will improve their management and the results obtained.

3. Empirical analysis

Because social capital dimensions are applicable to diverse organizational contexts and levels, the measurement of social capital is conditioned by the specific environment in which it is measured. Therefore, a valid measure of social capital in the academic context is necessary.

In a review of the management and organizational literature, we found various studies that use scales to measure the main dimensions of social capital (Chua, 2002; Chow and Chan, 2008). Nevertheless, none of these studies proposed a scale that could be used in the academic context. In contrast, papers in the scientometric literature usually measure the social capital of researchers through social network techniques (Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014; Li, Liao and Yen, 2013). Therefore, we opted to define our own instrument that can measure the particularities of social capital in research networks using a scale complemented with sociometric questions about network structure.

To do so, we performed a qualitative–quantitative study consisting of two steps. First, a Delphi panel was used to obtain an initial set of items to measure the relevant factors of social capital in academia. Based on experts' opinions, a questionnaire with 20 items was designed. In addition, the questionnaire was supplemented with five questions about the network, which enabled the collection of quantitative data necessary to measure the internal ties and the position occupied by researchers in the network. Second, exploratory and confirmatory factorial analyses were performed to validate the psychometric properties of the instrument.

3.1 The expert panel and questionnaire design

The Delphi method is widely used in the social sciences to obtain the consensus opinion of a group of experts on the determinant factors of the topic discussed (Landeta, 2006). In this study, Delphi analysis was applied to identify the key elements of social capital in academic research activity and its influence on research results. The participants on the expert panel should be principal investigators (PIs) from Spanish research teams from different scientific fields to avoid response bias. These experts had to satisfy two requirements: (1) they had to be members of teams recognized by the Spanish National Plan for Scientific Research, Development and Technological Innovation (National R+D+i Plan) and (2) they must have active and continuing research activity according to their performance records.

The PIs were informed by phone of the purpose of the research and that their participation was required. After sending several rounds of the questionnaire to participants, the final participants on the expert panel comprised 62 PIs from Spanish research teams. This panel provided a sufficiently large sample to guarantee the consistency of the panel results and represent a large number of knowledge areas, thereby avoiding response bias derived from this technique (Okoli and Pawloski, 2004).

Specifically, we sought to obtain information related to the various dimensions of social capital, as well as research policies, resources, incentives and research results. Based on the information collected from the responses of the PIs, 28 factors were identified and classified. This new document was sent to the original expert panel with a request for them to choose the factors that they considered relevant. Moreover, the document included an open field for the experts to make observations and suggestions. After two rounds, 45 valid responses had been received and the required consensus was achieved. This allowed us to design a final 20-item scale related to the three dimensions of social capital (Table 1).

Once the answers were obtained and analysed, a pretest of the questionnaire was performed.

After including the modifications gathered in the pretest, the initial version of the survey was designed.

Table 1. Social capital scale extracted from the expert panel

ITEM
The members of the research team...
1: Share our advances in research
2: Share resources
3: Exchange our knowledge and experiences
4: Share information
5: Seek and take advantage of synergies
6: Know and maintain contact with organizations and institutions
7: Hold regular meetings to advance the team's research activity
8: Hold meetings to define and design new research projects
9: Meet to discuss the progress of the doctoral theses directed by team members
10: Enjoy a good interpersonal climate
11: Agree on what is important in the research work
12: Share the same ambitions and visions in the research work
13: Are excited to achieve the goals and mission of the team
14: Try to help each other if we have any difficulty

- 15: Can trust that others will help us if necessary
- 16: Can trust that others will make the work easier
- 17: Maintain frequent interaction to improve our performance
- 18: Maintain interpersonal relationships very frequently
- 19: Exchange ideas with a large number of colleagues from outside the project team
- 20: Exchange ideas with a large number of professionals from outside our institution

3.2 Sample

Once the questionnaire was designed, it was sent by email to the vice-chancellors of research and the heads of departments of all Spanish universities for distribution to researchers. The email included a) a cover letter that briefly explained the purpose of the study and b) the link to the questionnaire form, where the researchers were asked to evaluate the significance of the measurement items using a 5-point Likert scale (a value of 1 represented *strongly disagree* and 5 represented *strongly agree*) and a set of complementary questions about the structure and management of the group (see Appendix 1). The data collection process was carried out between January-October 2017. The final sample size of the questionnaire was 1,798, consisting of 57.9% male and 42.1% female. Regarding professional category, 68.6% of researchers had tenured positions, while 29% had non-tenured positions. Finally, the sample was balanced with respect to knowledge fields, showing a distribution similar to that of the population data. Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the sample.

Table 2. Sample descriptive statistics

Variable	Descriptive statistics		Percentage
Gender	Male	962	57.9%
	Female	700	42.1%
	Total	1,662	100%
Academic rank	Tenured	1,120	68.5%
	Non-tenured	304	18.6%
	Junior researcher	169	10.3%
	Other position	43	2.6%
	Total	1,636	100%
	Field of knowledge	Arts and Humanities	217
Sciences		573	33.9%
Social Sciences and Legal Sciences		457	27.1%
Health Sciences		140	8.3%
Engineering and Architecture		301	17.8%
Total		1,688	100%

4. Results

To verify the appropriateness of the selected 20 items for measuring social capital, we applied two sequential factorial analyses. Factorial analysis is a technique in which factors are selected to explain the relationships among variables, looking for the minimum number of factors that explain the maximum information contained in the data. These analyses can be exploratory (the number of factors is not known a priori) or confirmatory (the factors are initially fixed). Both types of analysis were conducted to validate the item scale. The sample was subjected to a random procedure to split it into two equal parts (Brown, 2006). To analyse the internal structure of the construct, the first part of the sample was subjected to exploratory factorial analysis using SPSS. In the second step, we attempted to confirm the structure with the other half of the sample via confirmatory factor analysis through structural equation modelling using EQS (Bentler, 1995).

4.1 Exploratory factor analysis

To extract the dimensions of social capital in the academic context, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted. EFA is commonly used to reduce the set of the observed variables to a smaller and more parsimonious set of variables. Following the commonly applied rules, eigenvalues greater than 1.0 (Kaiser, 1974) as well as the examination of the sedimentation chart (Catell, 1966; Turker, 2009) were used to select the factors to include in the analysis. The sample size allowed high variance levels in the data, facilitating factor extraction and interpretation. We used the method of principal component analysis with varimax rotation, an orthogonal rotation, to simplify the interpretation of the factors since minimizes the number of variables that have high loadings on each factor and makes small loadings even smaller (Tang et al., 2018). Later subsequent confirmatory factor analysis was carried out to check the underlying structure among variables that initially proposes the principal component analysis. The adequacy of the factor analysis in our dataset was confirmed using Bartlett's test of sphericity (significance value < 0.05) and the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure of sampling adequacy ($0.938 > 0.70$) (Dziuban y Shirkey, 1974). To define each of the retained factors, we kept items with loads higher than 0.50 in a single factor. Hence, three items were excluded from the scale (6, 9 and 17) due to their statistical nonsignificance. The results of the EFA revealed three distinct factors (Table 3). Factor 1, labelled *relational social capital*, was composed of eight items related to trust, social climate, and sharing ambitions ($\alpha = 0.939$). Relational social capital also measured the extent to which research teams hold frequent meetings between members. With regard to the measurement of *cognitive social capital* (Factor 2), we collected information through seven items about the exchange of experience and knowledge, shared vision, information sharing, resources and advances among social network members ($\alpha = 0.932$). The measurement of *structural social*

capital (Factor 3) was composed of two items related to external network ties ($\alpha = 0.903$). Cronbach's alpha, a widely used measure of reliability, was obtained for each of the factors. Values greater than 0.7 are considered appropriate for Cronbach's alpha (Turkey, 2009; Tang et al., 2018). Table 3 shows the obtained factorial structure of the scale. The results of the factor analysis support the expected categorization of social capital into relational, cognitive and structural dimensions (Nahapiet and Ghosal, 1998). As expected based on the expert panel, social capital is a multidimensional construct.

Table 3 Exploratory factor analysis results

Item	Component (factor loadings)		
	1	2	3
<i>Relational dimension</i>			
15: We can trust that others will help us if necessary	0.833	0.330	0.086
16: We can trust that others will make the work easier	0.821	0.355	0.131
14: We try to help each other if we have any difficulty	0.801	0.367	0.106
10: We enjoy a good interpersonal climate	0.793	0.301	0.122
11: We agree on what is important in the research work	0.752	0.239	0.343
12: We share the same ambitions and visions in the research work	0.742	0.220	0.302
13: We are excited to achieve the goals and mission of the team	0.674	0.370	0.321
18: We maintain interpersonal relationships very frequently	0.525	0.410	0.322
<i>Cognitive dimension</i>			
7: We hold regular meetings to advances the team's research activity	0.173	0.811	0.294
1: We share our advances in research	0.368	0.801	0.127
3: We exchange our knowledge and experiences	0.478	0.775	0.171
4: We share information	0.483	0.749	0.155
5: We seek and take advantage of synergies	0.484	0.706	0.226
2: We share resources	0.314	0.686	-0.014
8: We hold meetings to define and design new research projects	0.171	0.670	0.443
<i>Structural dimension</i>			
20: We exchange ideas with a large number of professionals from outside our institution	0.202	0.148	0.888
19: We exchange ideas with a large number of colleagues from outside the project team	0.257	0.224	0.863

Eigenvalues	10.080	1.391	1.331
Total variance explained by each factor (%)	59.293	8.185	7.829
Cumulative variance explained by the factor (%)	59.293	67.478	75.307
Cronbach's alpha	0.939	0.932	0.903

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: 0.938

Bartlett's test of sphericity: Chi-square: 6589.339

df: 136

Significance: 0.000

*** significant at 1%

4.2. Confirmatory factor analysis

A confirmatory factorial analysis (CFA) was applied to evaluate the quality of the obtained factorial structure of the scale by testing how the model reflected the underlying theory. From the previous EFA, the scale was specified as a second-order model with three first-order factors (relational dimension, cognitive dimension and structural dimension) and a second-order factor (social capital). CFA was used to determine to what extent the proposed model fits the sample data, drawing on data obtained from the second subsample of academic researchers.

The initial analyses suggested that the dataset did not follow univariate or multivariate normality, showing an elliptical distribution. This was confirmed by the value of Mardia's coefficient (134.6446) and the analysis of asymmetry and kurtosis of the data. Therefore, we opted to estimate the model using an ordinary least squares method (Bentler, 2006). To confirm the measurement we applied specific confirmatory factorial analysis techniques such as convergent validity, construct reliability and content validity.

First, we analyse the convergent validity to verify that all of the proposed measurement items represented the construct of academic social capital. Model estimation confirmed that all factor loadings were significant at the 5% level and that the loadings on the general factor ranged from 0.5 to 0.7. Second, the correlation coefficient (ρ) was measured to assess the composite reliability. A $\rho > 0.75$ was deemed as representing good reliability. In our case, ρ was 0.98. In addition, the internal consistency of the scale was assessed by calculating Cronbach's alpha (0.954). Third, a measurement scale has the content validity, whether the items are representative and exhaustive and if the items test the contents and the theories. Through the results of the analysis of these three specific techniques, we consider appropriate the use of this scale to measure social capital.

Overall, the confirmatory factor analysis of the proposed three-factor, second-order social capital model demonstrated a good fit with the data ($N = 869$). The chi-squared test was significant (χ^2_{113}

= 512.260; $df = 133$; $p < 0.01$), but as has been recognized in the literature, the p-value becomes significant for large samples (Hooper et al., 2008). Alternative indices, both absolute and incremental, can be used to evaluate the model fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Specifically, in terms of absolute indices, we analysed (acceptable thresholds level in parentheses) the root mean square residual (RMR) = 0.047 (<0.8), standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) = 0.042 (<0.8), goodness-of-fit statistic (GFI) = 0.995 (>0.95) and the adjusted GFI (AGFI) = 0.993 (>0.95). In terms of incremental indices, we analysed the normed fit index (NFI) = 0.958 (>0.95), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), non-normed fit index (NNFI) = 0.960 (>0.95), and comparative fit index (CFI) = 0.967 (>0.95). Thus, the results corroborate the suitability of the three proposed factors (relational, cognitive and structural dimension) in the measurement of academic social capital. Figure 1 presents the proposed model.

Figure 1. Model of social capital scale

RMR = 0.047; SRMR = 0.042; GFI = 0.995; AGFI = 0.993; CFI = 0.9667; TLI = 0.960; NFI = 0.958

5. Conclusions and discussion

The evolution of science in recent decades has raised the importance of two elements that are basic to the development of knowledge-based societies: multidisciplinary and scientific collaboration (Hoekman, Frenken and Tijssen, 2010; Cummings and Kiesler, 2014; Coccia and Bozeman, 2016). Research is normally conducted by groups in which academics from different fields interact with researchers from different universities, institutions and/or firms (Cummings and Kiesler, 2014). The triple helix model (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff, 1999) emphasizes the active role of interdependent actors (university–industry–government) in the current knowledge creation process. In this framework, the university research system moves towards higher (deep and long–term) interaction with industry by applying the transdisciplinary Mode 2 of knowledge production (Dooley and Kirk, 2007; Bozeman, Fay and Slade, 2013).

The literature has highlighted the crucial role played by social capital in this context, facilitating knowledge sharing and improving research performance (Curseu et al., 2012; Phelps, Heidl and Wadhwa, 2012; Tsai et al., 2014). Higher levels of social capital encourage researchers to put their human capital at the disposal of other scholars, which contributes to the joint creation of knowledge. The scale proposed in this paper attempts to explain how these effects of social capital occur. Empirical studies in the academic context exploring this issue remain scarce and have almost exclusively relied on social network analysis techniques to measure the effects of social capital on researchers' performance (Abbasi et al., 2011; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). However, as science is increasingly organized around larger work groups and consortia (Cummings and Kiesler, 2014), it may be helpful to rely on the methods and techniques used in the organizational literature to measure and manage social capital. In addition, this scale allows us to measure the qualitative and behavioural dimensions of social capital, thus improving our understanding of the internal dynamics of research teams.

The results of the exploratory analysis suggest a second-order model with three first-order factors (relational dimension, structural dimension and cognitive dimension) and a second-order factor (social capital) as a reliable model of social capital in academia.

The confirmatory analysis reported indices that allowed us to verify the model fit. Alternative fit indices corroborated the good fit of the overall model with the data. This result leads us to conclude that the 20-item scale is valid and reliable and is suitable to measure social capital in academic research teams.

The utilization of the proposed scale provides interesting inputs that can be complemented with traditional social network techniques to measure social capital in an academic context. For this reason, the scale has been complemented with social network measures related to internal ties and the centrality of researchers in the network, which previous papers have highlighted as important attributes for evaluating structural social capital (Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt,

2013; Li, Liao and Yen, 2013). Density and centrality are the two most commonly analysed sociometric properties of networks in empirical research (Rice and Yoshioka-Maxwell, 2015). Density concerns information about the average level of communication between members (Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila, 2016), and ‘represents the actual number of direct ties as a function of the possible number of ties in a network of a given size’ (Rice and Yoshioka-Maxwell, 2015:376). Centrality provides information on the prominence of some actors in the network (Rice and Yoshioka-Maxwell, 2015); central actors have a structurally advantageous position in the network compared with less central actors (Badar et al., 2015). The standard centrality measures are degree centrality, closeness centrality and betweenness centrality, and each provides different benefits. The first provides knowledge sharing, the second provides a quick flow of knowledge and the third provides brokerage and control of knowledge (Badar et al., 2015). The instrument offers deeper information that improves understanding of the underlying mechanisms through which the social capital of academic research teams is built.

The results of the factor analysis support the expected categorization of social capital embedded in academic research teams into relational, cognitive and structural dimensions (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). The multidimensional nature of the construct provides useful information regarding the internal dynamics within the social capital construct. The *relational* dimension of interpersonal dynamics that exist within the research team largely motivates the team to share and create knowledge, contributing strongly to the building of social capital. On the other hand, the *cognitive* dimension, which is related to language and the common context, and the *structural* dimension of the external relationships of researchers appear to make a significant, albeit weaker, contribution to the building of research social capital. Given that the results demonstrate the psychometric validity of the questionnaire as a measure of social capital embedded in university research teams, as well as the lack of survey-based instruments in the academic research literature, the scale proposed in this paper offers a starting point for further empirical analysis.

This study was conducted with a considerable number of research teams belonging to Spanish universities. However, it would be appropriate to extend the empirical analysis to universities from different countries to verify the results.

The proposed scale could provide relevant criteria for the management of social capital in research teams. In knowledge-based societies, universities are the largest producer of the knowledge demanded by society, and the literature shows that the social capital of research teams has positive effects on the productivity of researchers (Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). Encouraging a climate of trust and co-operation, a good interpersonal climate, frequent relationships and common objectives among research team members could significantly improve researchers’ performance. In addition, the proposed scale elucidates relevant criteria to promote the exchange of knowledge and experiences within the group, the sharing of resources and information, and the exchange of ideas with colleagues outside the project or institution.

Recent decades have seen a significant increase in both domestic and international scientific collaboration. Advanced research increasingly requires the participation of multidisciplinary groups integrating scientists from diverse backgrounds who contribute complementary assets and skills (Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt, 2013; Perry-Smith and Vincent, 2008; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). A variety of papers have examined scientific collaboration within multidisciplinary groups and found that groups that included more disciplines reported better performance (Cummings and Kiesler, 2005; Porac et al, 2004). However, high levels of multidisciplinary can also have negative effects on research performance because of increased conflict, decreased identification, and problems of cohesion and co-operation (Cummings and Kiesler, 2005; Yong et al., 2014). This fact suggests an inverted U-shaped curvilinear relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance. The social capital of research teams can play a moderating role in this relationship. If it is adequately measured and managed, social capital can make multidisciplinary research teams perform better, decreasing the negative effects and fostering the positive influence of multidisciplinary on research productivity.

As noted, knowing the social capital of researchers is very useful because it is an asset that affects the processes and performance of research teams. The measurement instrument proposed in this paper has a variety of implications. Table 4 presents the different uses and practical implications of the proposed instrument at three levels, distinguishing between financial institutions, universities and research teams.

Table 4. Potential use of the social capital scale

	Management	Evaluation
Research team level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of the composition of consortia • Analysis the structure of informal research teams / networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and promoting the ability to build networks
Universities level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of training policies • Identification and development of potential strategic alliances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of research groups' ability to build and participate in networks
Financial entities level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help to build research networks through research funding programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of research teams' participating in calls to develop scientific networks

The proposed scale would have implications concerning the scope of management and evaluation at the research team level and above (universities and financial entities). At the research team level, the instrument could be used to identify potential partners with good social capital to build consortia. Internally, it would reveal the informal structure of the group itself, for example, by detecting whether a researcher is well connected externally or whether there is an internal node that helps the cohesion of the research team. Better knowledge of the informal structure of the team would allow measures to build external networks to be adopted. At the university level, the scale could be used to guide training policies by encouraging group members to build networks and strategic alliances. Finally, at the level of funding entities, it would serve to measure the capacity of the science system to build research spaces that integrate research within the scope of a call for projects. The scale could be a good tool to evaluate the capacity of the research teams that attend the calls to properly develop the research.

As noted, the scale could have practical implications at the group, university and financial entity levels. It would be interesting for future research to undertake a multilevel analysis based on these data, analysing how the different dimensions of social capital measured in the scale affect the development of scientific productivity at the three levels.

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Appendix 1. Questionnaire of social capital

The aim of our research is to build a scale for measuring social capital. We request that you give us your opinion on a series of questions related to your activity as a researcher belonged to a research team. It will take no more than 5 minutes. All the data you provide us will be treated in an aggregated and anonymous way, with strictly academic objectives, so your answers will be completely confidential.

Researcher information		
Name:		
University:		
Gender:	Position:	Scientific field:
Number of members in your research team:	Are you PI of the research team? Y/N	
Have you co-authored with members of your team? Y/N	If yes, please indicate the number:	
Who are your co-authors and how many papers have you published with each one? (Please, add as many rows as you consider necessary):		
Co-author Name: _____	Number of papers co-authored: ____	
Co-author Name: _____	Number of papers co-authored: ____	
.....	
Co-author Name: _____	Number of papers co-authored: ____	

Please indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements:	Strongly disagree		Strongly agree		
	1	2	3	4	5
Team members can trust that others will help them if necessary	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members can trust that others will make work easier	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members enjoy a good interpersonal climate	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members try to help each other if they have any difficulty	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The team members agree on what was important in the research work	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The team members knew and maintained contact with organizations and institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members have a frequent interaction to improve our performance	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members share the same ambitions and visions in the research work	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members maintain interpersonal relationships very often	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members are excited to achieve the goals and objectives of the team	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members hold regular meetings to advance the team's research activity	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members exchange our knowledge and experiences	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members share resources	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members share information	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members share our advances in research	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members look for and take advantage of synergies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members hold meetings to define and design new research projects	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The members of the team meet to discuss the progress of the doctoral theses directed by team members	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members exchange ideas with a large number of colleagues outside the team	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Team members exchange ideas with a large number of professionals from outside our institution	<input type="checkbox"/>				